

Causality, classical bivalent logic and probability theory

Ilija BARUKČIĆ^{a,1},

^a*Horandstrasse, 26441 Jever, Germany*

Abstract. Aim: A statistical methodology based analysis of causal relationships and chains of causation in life sciences, medicine, and other sciences by logically consistent methods backed by empirical data is still not generally accepted.

Methods: In this publication, the relationship between a cause and an effect is re-analysed again while using the tools of classical logic and probability theory.

Results: The mathematical formula of the causal relationship k has been derived mathematically from the axiom $+1 = +1$.

Conclusion: Experimental and non-experimental can be analysed by the methods presented for causal relationships.

Keywords. cause, effect, causality, causation, causal relationship

Introduction

There is always something to learn about objective reality [1], causes and effects and the scientific tools describing the same in a logically consistent way. However and besides of all, it is vital to consider too whether there exists something like causes and an effects at all? In particular, what are the epistemological consequences if we describe something mathematically which may not exist at all? Therefore, in order to prevent any misunderstandings right from the beginning, in the further course of this work, we just *assume* that causes and effects are existing independently and outside of human mind and consciousness, objectively and real. As is well known, an **assumption** should not be confused with a **proof** as such. Thus far, what is so exciting about the relationship between cause and effect, why should we care about the nature of causation at all? Historically, causation was important for many[2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28] even if not mentioned here but not for all. The history of denialism of causality in Philosophy, Mathematics, Statistics[see 29, p. 128], Physics [30] and a number of other disciplines too is very long and rich of ideas and proposals. In an exemplary manner it should be noted that notable proponents of *conditionalism*[31]

¹Corresponding Author: Ilija Barukčić, Horandstrasse, 26441 Jever, Germany; (Published: February 13, 2021); E-mail: ibarukcic@yandex.ru.

like the German physiologist Max Richard Constantin Verworn [32] (1863 - 1921) and the German anatomist and pathologist David Paul von Hansemann [33] (1858 - 1920) and of course other authors too favoured conditions one-sidedly with no objective reason. In his essay “Kausale und konditionale Weltanschauung” Verworn himself ignores cause and effect relationships completely. Verworn demands: “**Das Ding ist also identisch mit der Gesamtheit seiner Bedingungen.**”[32, 31] In physical sciences, the German physicist Werner Karl Heisenberg (1901 - 1976) attacked the principle of causality by his uncertainty principle[30]. Heisenberg wrote: “**Weil alle Experimente den Gesetzen der Quantenmechanik und damit der Gleichung (1) unterworfen sind, so wird durch die Quantenmechanik die Ungültigkeit des Kausalgesetzes definitiv festgestellt.**”[30] while ‘Gleichung (1)’ denotes Heisenberg’s uncertainty principle. However, in order to avoid further difficulties it therefore appears necessary to clarify that Heisenberg’s uncertainty principle is meanwhile identified as a logical fallacy and refuted [34, 35, 36]. We must not forget that as scientific history has continued, with all its glories and its shame, we had to learn from it that the various obstacles and particular difficulties with respect to different scientific issues including causation too were simply small and intermediate steps on which scientist ceaselessly climb upwards to new scientific insights and the most possible heights of scientific findings. To put it plainly, it is by no means a hopeless endeavour to try to address the relationship between a cause and an effect in accordance with the basic laws of classical bivalent logic, statistics and probability theory.

1. Material and methods

2.2. Definitions

The trial to establish a generally valid mathematical **concept of causation based on classical bivalent logic** is aggravated by many countless attacks on the principle of causality too. However, at least since George Boole’s (1815 - 1864) mathematization of classical bivalent logic[4, 5] we possess the scientific methodology to approach step by step to the solution of the problem of causality mathematically. Classical bivalent logic is based on Boolean variables too, named after George Boole, with the two truth values either +0 or +1. Logical connectives (also called logical operators) like conjunction (denoted as \wedge), disjunction (denoted as \vee) or negation (denoted as \neg) et cetera do not only conjoin two statements P_t and Q_t to form another statement but real world events at a given (period of) time / Bernoulli[37] trial[38] t or even at different Bernoulli trials (time series [18]) too. Strategically, this enable us to express conditions like necessary and sufficient **conditions** et cetera mathematically while using the tools of probability theory. Nonetheless, despite Boole’s excellent and outstanding contribution to classical logic, it is however noteworthy that Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz (1646 - 1716) himself published already 1703 the first self-consistent binary[39] number system [40, 41] representing all numeric values while using typically +0 (zero, false) and +1 (one, true).

2.2.1. The number +0

Definition 1 (The number +0) *The number +0 is defined [24, 25, 26, 27, 28] as the expression*

$$+0 \equiv (+1) \times (+0) \equiv (+0) \times (+1) \equiv +1 - 1 \quad (1)$$

2.2.2. The number +1

Definition 2 (The number +1) The number +1 is defined [24, 25, 26, 27, 28] as the expression

$$+1 \equiv +1 + 0 \equiv +1 - 0 \quad (2)$$

2.2.3. The probability of a single event

Definition 3 (The probability of a single event)

In consideration of the definitions before, let ${}_R U_t$ denote the cause (in German: die Ursache) from the point of view of a stationary observer[42], let ${}_R W_t$ denote the effect (in German: die Wirkung) from the point of view of a stationary observer[42], let $p({}_R U_t)$ represent the probability of a single event (i. e. cause) ${}_R U_t$ at Bernoulli trial t , let $p({}_R W_t)$ represent the probability of a single event (i. e. effect) ${}_R W_t$ at Bernoulli trial t . Let $\Psi({}_R U_t)$ represent the wavefunction, a probability amplitude [43] of an event or of finding an event inside a set at a given (period of) time / Bernoulli trial [38] t . Let $\Psi^*({}_R U_t)$ denote the complex conjugate of the wave-function. In general, the probability of a single[see 44, p. 72] cause is determined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p({}_R U_t) &\equiv p({}_R U_t) \\
 &\equiv p({}_R U_t) \times (+1) \\
 &\equiv p({}_R U_t) \times \frac{({}_R U_t)}{({}_R U_t)} \\
 &\equiv \frac{p({}_R U_t) \times ({}_R U_t)}{({}_R U_t)} \\
 &\equiv \frac{E({}_R U_t)}{{}_R U_t} \\
 &\equiv p({}_R U_t) \times \frac{p({}_R U_t) \times ({}_R U_t \times {}_R U_t)}{p({}_R U_t) \times ({}_R U_t \times {}_R U_t)} \\
 &\equiv \frac{p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R U_t) \times ({}_R U_t \times {}_R U_t)}{p({}_R U_t) \times ({}_R U_t \times {}_R U_t)} \\
 &\equiv \frac{E({}_R U_t)^2}{E({}_R U_t^2)} \\
 &\equiv \Psi({}_R U_t) \times \Psi^*({}_R U_t)
 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In general, a cause may increase or decrease the probability[11, 12, 13, 15] of its own effect. The probability of a single effect is determined as

$$\begin{aligned}
p({}_R W_t) &\equiv p({}_R W_t) \\
&\equiv p({}_R W_t) \times (+1) \\
&\equiv p({}_R W_t) \times \left(\frac{{}_R W_t}{{}_R W_t} \right) \\
&\equiv \frac{p({}_R W_t) \times ({}_R W_t)}{({}_R W_t)} \\
&\equiv \frac{E({}_R W_t)}{{}_R W_t} \\
&\equiv p({}_R W_t) \times \frac{p({}_R W_t) \times ({}_R W_t \times {}_R W_t)}{p({}_R W_t) \times ({}_R W_t \times {}_R W_t)} \\
&\equiv \frac{p({}_R W_t) \times p({}_R W_t) \times ({}_R W_t \times {}_R W_t)}{p({}_R W_t) \times ({}_R W_t \times {}_R W_t)} \\
&\equiv \frac{E({}_R W_t)^2}{E({}_R W_t^2)} \\
&\equiv \Psi({}_R W_t) \times \Psi^*({}_R W_t)
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

The case of continuous random variables has already been treated [18] too.

2.2.4. The n-th moment expectation value

Definition 4 (The n-th moment expectation value)

Let ${}_R U_t$ denote an event (at a certain (period of) time or **Bernoulli trial t** [38]). Let $p({}_R U_t)$ represent the probability of an event at a given Bernoulli trial t. Let $E({}_R U_t^n)$ denote the n-th moment **expectation value** [45, 46] of ${}_R U_t$. Let $E({}_R U_t^1)$ denote the first moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$. Let $E({}_R U_t^2)$ denote the second moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$. In general, **the n-th moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$** is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
E({}_R U_t^n) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R U_t^1 \times \dots}_{(n\text{-times})} \right) \times p({}_R U_t) \\
&\equiv ({}_R U_t^n) \times p({}_R U_t)
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Furthermore, it is

$$\begin{aligned}
E({}_R U_t^n)^m &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R U_t^1 \times \dots}_{(n\text{-times})} \right)^m \times p({}_R U_t)^m \\
&\equiv ({}_R U_t^n)^m \times p({}_R U_t)^m
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

The first moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned}
E\left({}_R U_t^1\right) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R U_t^1}_{(one-times)} \right) \times p({}_R U_t) \\
&\equiv \left({}_R U_t^1 \right) \times p({}_R U_t) \\
&\equiv ({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R U_t)
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

The second moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned}
E\left({}_R U_t^2\right) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R U_t^1}_{(two-times)} \right) \times p({}_R U_t) \\
&\equiv \left({}_R U_t^2 \right) \times p({}_R U_t)
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

2.2.5. The n-th moment expectation value of anti U

Definition 5 (The n-th moment expectation value of anti U) Let $p({}_R U_t)$ represent the probability of a single event ${}_R U_t$ at a given Bernoulli trial t . Let $(1-p({}_R U_t))$ represent the probability that a single event ${}_R U_t$ will not occur, will not exist at a given Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R \underline{U}_t^n)$ denote the n-th moment **expectation value** [45, 46] of anti ${}_R U_t$. Let $E({}_R \underline{U}_t^1)$ denote the first moment expectation value of anti ${}_R U_t$. Let $E({}_R \underline{U}_t^2)$ denote the second moment expectation value of anti ${}_R U_t$. In general, **the n-th moment expectation value of anti ${}_R U_t$** , denoted by ${}_R \underline{U}_t$, is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
E({}_R \underline{U}_t^n) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R U_t^1 \times \dots}_{(n-times)} \right) \times (1-p({}_R U_t)) \\
&\equiv ({}_R \underline{U}_t^n) \times (1-p({}_R U_t))
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

The first moment expectation value of anti ${}_R U_t$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned}
E\left({}_R \underline{U}_t^1\right) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R U_t^1}_{(one-times)} \right) \times (1-p({}_R U_t)) \\
&\equiv \left({}_R U_t^1 \right) \times (1-p({}_R U_t)) \\
&\equiv ({}_R U_t) \times (1-p({}_R U_t))
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

The second moment expectation value of anti ${}_R U_t$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned}
E\left({}_R \underline{U}_t^2\right) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R U_t^1}_{(two-times)} \right) \times (1-p({}_R U_t)) \\
&\equiv \left({}_R U_t^2 \right) \times (1-p({}_R U_t))
\end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

2.2.6. The n -th moment expectation value of U and W

Definition 6 (The n -th moment expectation value of U and W) Let $p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$ represent the joint probability of an occurring of the events ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$ at the same (period of time or) Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R U_t^n, {}_R W_t^n)$ denote the n -th moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$. Let $E({}_R U_t^1)$ denote the first moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$. In general, **the n -th moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$** is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_R U_t^n, {}_R W_t^n) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{({}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R W_t^1) \times ({}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R W_t^1) \times \dots}_{(n\text{-times})} \right) \times p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) \\ &\equiv ({}_R U_t^n \times {}_R W_t^n) \times p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The first moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_R U_t^1, {}_R W_t^1) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R W_t^1}_{(one\text{-times})} \right) \times p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) \\ &\equiv ({}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R W_t^1) \times p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) \\ &\equiv ({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \times p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

2.2.7. The variance

Definition 7 (The variance) Sir Ronald Aylmer Fisher (1890 – 1962) coined the term variance as known: “It is therefore desirable **in analysing the causes** of variability to deal with the square of the standard deviation as the measure of variability. We shall term this quantity the Variance ... ”[see 47, p. 399]. Fisher, an English statistician, and may be “the single most important figure in 20th century statistics”[48], relates already variance and causes in the same context. Again, let $p({}_R U_t)$ represent the probability of a single event ${}_R U_t$ at a given point in space-time or Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R U_t)$ denote again the expectation value of ${}_R U_t$. The expectation value of a single event ${}_R U_t$ is defined as

$$E({}_R U_t) \equiv p({}_R U_t) \times ({}_R U_t) \equiv \Psi({}_R U_t) \times {}_R U_t \times \Psi^*({}_R U_t) \quad (14)$$

The expectation value of the other of ${}_R U_t$, of the complementary [24, 27] of ${}_R U_t$, of the opposite of ${}_R U_t$, of **the anti ${}_R U_t$** , denoted by ${}_{\bar{R}} U_t$, is defined as

$$E({}_{\bar{R}} U_t) \equiv (1 - p({}_R U_t)) \times ({}_R U_t) \quad (15)$$

In this context, $E({}_R U_t^2)$ is the expectation value of the second moment of ${}_R U_t$. The expectation value of ${}_R U_t^2$ is defined as

$$E({}_R U_t^2) \equiv p({}_R U_t) \times ({}_R U_t^2) \equiv p({}_R U_t) \times ({}_R U_t \times {}_R U_t) \quad (16)$$

Let $\sigma({}_R U_t)$ denote the standard deviation of ${}_R U_t$. Let $\sigma({}_R U_t)^2$ denote the variance of ${}_R U_t$. In general, the variance [see 49, p. 42] is defined[24, 27] as

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma({}_R U_t)^2 &\equiv \sigma({}_R U_t) \times \sigma({}_R U_t) \\
&\equiv E({}_R U_t - E({}_R U_t))^2 \\
&\equiv E({}_R U_t^2) - (E({}_R U_t))^2 \\
&\equiv ({}_R U_t^2 \times p({}_R U_t)) - (p({}_R U_t) \times {}_R U_t)^2 \\
&\equiv ({}_R U_t^2) \times (p({}_R U_t) - p({}_R U_t)^2) \\
&\equiv ({}_R U_t^2) \times (p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))) \\
&\equiv {}_R U_t \times (p({}_R U_t) \times {}_R U_t \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))) \\
&\equiv E({}_R U_t) \times {}_R U_t \times (1 - p({}_R U_t)) \\
&\equiv E({}_R U_t) \times E(\underline{{}_R U_t})
\end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

From equation 17 follows that

$${}_R U_t \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)}{\sqrt{p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))}} \tag{18}$$

and that

$${}_R W_t \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R W_t)}{\sqrt{p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t))}} \tag{19}$$

2.2.8. The n-th moment co-variance

Definition 8 (The n-th moment co-variance)

Let $p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$ represent the joint probability of ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$ at the same (period of time) Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R U_t^n, {}_R W_t^n)$ denote the n-th moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$. Let $E({}_R U_t^n)$ denote the n-th moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$. Let $E({}_R W_t^n)$ denote the n-th moment expectation value of ${}_R W_t$. Let $\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$ denote the co-variance between ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$. In general, **the n-th moment co-variance between ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$** is defined[24] as

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma({}_R U_t^n, {}_R W_t^n) &\equiv ({}_R U_t^n \times {}_R W_t^n) \times (p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t))) \\
&\equiv (({}_R U_t^n \times {}_R W_t^n \times p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)) - (({}_R U_t^n \times {}_R W_t^n) \times p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t))) \\
&\equiv E({}_R U_t^n, {}_R W_t^n) - ({}_R U_t^n \times p({}_R U_t)) \times ({}_R W_t^n \times p({}_R W_t)) \\
&\equiv E({}_R U_t^n, {}_R W_t^n) - (E({}_R U_t^n) \times E({}_R W_t^n))
\end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

From equation 20 follows equally that

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t, {}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t) &\equiv ({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t \times {}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t) \times (p({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t, {}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t) - (p({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t) \times p({}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t))) \\
&\equiv (({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t \times {}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t \times p({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t, {}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t)) - (({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t \times {}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t) \times p({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t) \times p({}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t))) \\
&\equiv E({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t, {}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t) - ({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t \times p({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t)) \times ({}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t \times p({}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t)) \\
&\equiv E({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t, {}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t) - (E({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t) \times E({}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t))
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Equation 21 demands too that

$${}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t \times {}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t, {}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t)}{(p({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t, {}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t) - (p({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t) \times p({}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t)))} \tag{22}$$

2.2.9. Independence

Definition 9 (Independence)

In general, an event ${}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t$ at the Bernoulli trial t need not but can be independent of the existence or of the occurrence of another event ${}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t$ at the same Bernoulli trial t . Mathematically, independence [50, 51] in terms of probability [see 49, p. 9] theory is defined at the same (period of) time t (i. e. Bernoulli trial t) as

$$p({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t \wedge {}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t) \equiv p({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t) \times p({}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t) \tag{23}$$

or as

$$p({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t \wedge {}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t \wedge C_t \wedge \dots) \equiv p({}_{\mathbb{R}}U_t) \times p({}_{\mathbb{R}}W_t) \times p(C_t) \times \dots \tag{24}$$

Remark 1 *Logic and probability theory are one of the most important scientific pillars in the formal study of relationships between events. However, what is the significance of the law of independence with respect to the principle of causality? And here is one of the deepest question of all: is there a deterministic relationship between cause and effect given at all if both, cause and effect, are equally independent of each other. To express it differently: the law of independence of probability theory defines causation to some extent **ex negativo** and has the potential to provide a far reaching mathematical answer to one of the fundamental questions of physics and science as such, the relationship between cause and effect. The relationship between a cause and an effect can be analyzed under different conditions and from numerous perspectives. In point of fact, what happens to the cause-effect relationship under dynamic conditions where **only one single cause interacts with its own single effect**? In other words, may a certain, single effect fail to occur in the presence of its own, single cause (see table 1, Bernoulli trial 2) and the either way. May a certain, single effect occur in the absence of its own, single cause (see table 1, Bernoulli trial 3). However, independent of the scientific method used to describe the relationship between a cause and an effect, it does not, therefore, make much sense to assume a deterministic relationship between a cause and an effect, under conditions of the existence of only one cause and one effect, if an effect may occur whether or not a cause is given. In this context, view aspects of the theory of causality of the German idealist philosopher Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel (1770-1831) are worth being mentioned. Following Hegel “Cause is cause only in so far as it produces an effect,*

and cause is nothing but this determination to have an effect ... "[see 52, p. 559] (see table 1, Bernoulli trial 1). Consequently, "... in so far as cause has not yet acted, or if it has ceased to act, then it is not cause, and effect in so far as its cause has vanished, is no longer effect but an indifferent actuality. "[see 52, p. 559] (see table 1, Bernoulli trial 3). In general, following Hegel, "... Thus, in the causal relation, cause and effect are inseparable; a cause which had no effect would not be a cause, just as an effect which had no cause would no longer be an effect. ... "[see 52, p. 151]. In point of fact, "... a cause which had no effect would not be a cause ... "[see 52, p. 151] (see table 1, Bernoulli trial 2). These and similar issues are illustrated in detail by the four basic Bernoulli trials as presented by table 1.

Table 1. Causal relationship under conditions of classical logic

Bernoulli trial t	$R U_t$	$R W_t$	$(R U_t \wedge R W_t) \equiv (R U_t \times R W_t)$
1	+1	+1	+1
2	+1	+0	+0
3	+0	+1	+0
4	+0	+0	+0
...

2.2.10. Dependence

Definition 10 (Dependence)

The dependence of events [see 15, p. 57-61] is defined as

$$p\left(\underbrace{R U_t \wedge R W_t \wedge C_t \wedge \dots}_n\right) \equiv \sqrt[n]{\underbrace{p(R U_t) \times p(R W_t) \times p(C_t) \times \dots}_n} \quad (25)$$

2.2.11. Causal relationship k

Definition 11 (Causal relationship k)

Nonetheless, mathematically, the causal relationship [15, 18, 19, 21, 22] between a cause $R U_t$ (German: Ursache) and an effect $R W_t$ (German: Wirkung), denoted by $k(R U_t, R W_t)$, is defined at each single Bernoulli trial t in terms of statistics and probability theory as

$$\begin{aligned} k(R U_t, R W_t) &\equiv \frac{\sigma(R U_t, R W_t)}{\sigma(R U_t) \times \sigma(R W_t)} \\ &\equiv \frac{p(R U_t \wedge R W_t) - p(R U_t) \times p(R W_t)}{\sqrt{(p(R U_t) \times (1 - p(R U_t))) \times (p(R W_t) \times (1 - p(R W_t)))}} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where $\sigma ({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$ denotes the co-variance between a cause ${}_R U_t$ and an effect ${}_R W_t$ at every **single Bernoulli trial** t , $\sigma ({}_R U_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of a cause ${}_R U_t$ at the same **single Bernoulli trial** t , $\sigma ({}_R W_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of an effect ${}_R W_t$ at same **single Bernoulli trial** t . Table 2 illustrates the theoretically possible relationships between a cause and an effect at a certain **single Bernoulli trial** t .

Table 2. Sample space and the causal relationship k

		Effect B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Cause	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(U_t)$
A_t	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{U}_t)$
		$p(W_t)$	$p(\underline{W}_t)$	+1

2.3. Axioms

2.3.1. Axiom I. Lex identitatis

In this context, we define[24] axiom I or lex identitatis as

$$+1 = +1 \quad (27)$$

Lex identitatis is an axiom which possess the potential to serve as the most basic and equally as the most simple axiom of science. In point of fact, how can something be **identical with itself**[53, 54, 55, 56] and in the same respect different from itself. An increasingly popular view on identity is the one advocated by Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz (1646-1716):

“Chaque chose est ce qu’elle est.
Et dans autant d’exemples qu’on voudra
A est A,
B est B.”
[57]

or **A = A, B = B** or **+1 = +1**. Exactly in complete compliance with Leibniz, Johann Gottlieb Fichte (1762 - 1814) elaborates on the same issue as follows:

“Each thing is what it is ;
it has those realities which are posited when it is posited,
(A = A.) ”
[58]

2.3.2. Axiom II. Lex contradictionis

In this context[24], axiom II or **lex contradictionis**, the negative of lex identitatis, or

$$+0 = +1 \quad (28)$$

is of no minor importance too. The fact that a logical contradiction as formulated by axiom II can be a starting point of reasoning does not necessarily imply that para-consistent logic [59, 60, 61, 62, 63, 64] is correct as such.

2.3.3. Axiom III. Lex negationis

$$\neg(0) \times 0 = 1 \quad (29)$$

where \neg denotes (logical [5] or natural) negation[24]. In this context, there is some evidence that $\neg(1) \times 1 = 0$. In other words, it is $(\neg(1) \times 1) \times (\neg(0) \times 0) = 1$.

3. Results

3.1. The causal relationship k

Theorem 1 (Causal relationship k) *Thus far, let $p({}_R U_t)$ represent the probability from the point of view of a stationary observer R of a certain cause ${}_R U_t$ (in German: U like *Ursache*), i. e. a random variable or a quantum mechanical observable or a cluster inside a set, at a certain Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R U_t^2)$ denote the expectation value of the cause ${}_R U_t^2$. Let $E({}_R U_t)$ denote the expectation value of the cause ${}_R U_t$. Let $\sigma({}_R U_t)$ denote the standard deviation of the cause ${}_R U_t$. Let $\sigma({}_R U_t)^2$ denote the variance of the cause ${}_R U_t$. Let $p({}_R W_t)$ represent the probability from the point of view of a stationary observer R of its own effect ${}_R W_t$ (in German: W like *Wirkung*), i. e. a random variable or a quantum mechanical observable or a cluster inside a set, at a certain Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R W_t^2)$ denote the expectation value of the effect ${}_R W_t^2$. Let $E({}_R W_t)$ denote the expectation value of the effect ${}_R W_t$. Let $\sigma({}_R W_t)$ denote the standard deviation of the effect ${}_R W_t$. Let $\sigma({}_R W_t)^2$ denote the variance of the effect ${}_R W_t$. Let $\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$ denote the co-variance of cause ${}_R U_t$ and effect ${}_R W_t$. The causal relationship, denoted as $k({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$, inside a sets can be calculated as*

$$\begin{aligned}
k({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) &\equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)}{\sqrt{\sigma({}_R U_t)^2 \times \sigma({}_R W_t)^2}} \\
&\equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)}{\sigma({}_R U_t) \times \sigma({}_R W_t)} \\
&\equiv \frac{({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \times (p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t)))}{\sqrt{(({}_R U_t)^2) \times (p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))) \times ({}_R W_t)^2 \times (p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t)))}} \\
&\equiv \frac{({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \times (p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t)))}{({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \times \sqrt{((p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))) \times (p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t)))}} \\
&\equiv \frac{(p({}_R U_t \wedge {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t)))}{\sqrt{((p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))) \times (p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t)))}}
\end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

Proof 1 (Proof by modus ponens.) If the premise

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{\text{(Premise)}} \tag{31}$$

is true, **then** the conclusion

$$k({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)}{\sigma({}_R U_t) \times \sigma({}_R W_t)} \tag{32}$$

is also true, the absence of any technical errors presupposed. The premise or respectively axiom I

$$+1 \equiv +1 \tag{33}$$

is true. Multiplying this premise (i. e. axiom I) by the a single cause (${}_R U_t$) at a certain Bernoulli trial t , it is

$$({}_R U_t) \equiv ({}_R U_t) \tag{34}$$

Multiplying the cause (equation 34) by its own effect (${}_R W_t$) it is

$$({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \equiv ({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \tag{35}$$

This basic relationship between a cause and an effect as described by equation 35 may be of use especially under conditions of classical logic (either +0 or +1 values) and is illustrated in detail by table 3.

It should be noted at this early stage that we will not further discuss at this point the relationship $1^1 \times 1^1 \equiv 1^2$ or the relationship $0^1 \times 0^1 \equiv 0^2$ [26]. As a side effect, table 3 provide an evidence of the identity of the logical operation, denoted by \wedge , and the algebraic operation multiplication. However, as soon as ${}_R U_t$ or ${}_R W_t$ take on other values than either +0 or +1, the previous relationship (equation 35) is not appropriate enough

Table 3. Causal relationship under conditions of classical logic

Bernoulli trial t	${}_R U_t$	${}_R W_t$	$({}_R U_t \wedge {}_R W_t) \equiv ({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t)$
1	+1	+1	+1
2	+1	+0	+0
3	+0	+1	+0
4	+0	+0	+0
...

to describe the causal relationship completely and may lead to a **cum hoc ergo propter hoc** logical fallacy [65]. In general, it is necessary to deal with such circumstances too. According to equation 18 it is

$${}_R U_t \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))}} \quad (36)$$

with the consequence that equation 35 changes to

$$({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \equiv \left(\frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))}} \right) \times {}_R W_t \quad (37)$$

According to equation 19 it is

$${}_R W_t \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R W_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t))}} \quad (38)$$

Therefore, equation 37 changes to

$$({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \equiv \left(\frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))}} \right) \times \left(\frac{\sigma({}_R W_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t))}} \right) \quad (39)$$

According to definition 8, equation 22, it is

$${}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)}{(p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t)))} \quad (40)$$

Simplifying equation 39, it is

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)}{(p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t)))} \right) &\equiv \\ &\left(\frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))}} \right) \\ &\times \left(\frac{\sigma({}_R W_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t))}} \right) \quad (41) \end{aligned}$$

Further rearrangement of equation 41 yields the causal relationship between the cause ${}_R U_t$ and the effect ${}_R W_t$, denoted as $k({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$, as

$$\begin{aligned} k({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) &\equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)}{\sigma({}_R U_t) \times \sigma({}_R W_t)} \\ &\equiv \frac{(p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t)))}{\sqrt{p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t)) \times p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t))}} \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

Quod erat demonstrandum.

Remark 2 To cut a long story short, it is necessary and inevitable to move away from confusing and logically inconsistent theories of causation. In this context, structural equation modelling (SEM) or counterfactual [66, 67, 68, 69] theories of causation (see table 1, Bernoulli trial 4) et cetera failed to provide a coherent mathematical foundation for the analysis of cause and effect relationships. Especially Sewall Wright [see 70, p. 557] has been one of the first to derive a kind of a structural equation modelling from the coefficient of correlation. Wright himself elaborates on this issue as follows: “The present paper is an attempt to present a method of measuring the direct influence along each separate path in such a system and thus of finding the degree to which variation of a given effect is determined by each particular cause. The method depends on the combination of knowledge of the degrees of correlation among the variables in a system with such knowledge as may be possessed of the causal relations” [see 70, p. 557]. Wright is pointing out that “**The method depends on the ... correlation among the variables ...**” [see 70, p. 557]. The causal relationship $k({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$, in contrast to Pearl’s $do(X=x)$ operator [see 71, p. 204], provide a logically consistent mathematical alternative to the structure equation modelling. Only under conditions where **the probability of events is constant from Bernoulli trial t to Bernoulli trial t** , we obtain the relationship

$$k({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) \equiv \frac{N \times N \times \sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)}{N \times \sigma({}_R U_t) \times N \times \sigma({}_R W_t)} \quad (43)$$

but not in general!

4. Discussion

The causal relationship k as proofed and derived by theorem 1 is a statistical method or procedure which is of use to analyse data for cause effect relationships. Nonetheless, a well-informed and critical reader may tend to believe to recognise the trace of Bravais [72] (1811-1863) - Pearson’s (1857-1936) “*product - moment coefficient of correlation*” [73, 74] inside the causal relationship k [15, 18, 19, 21, 75, 22]. Therefore, it is of great importance to bear in mind the fundamental differences between **Bravais - Pearson’s product-moment coefficient of correlation** and the causal relationship k .

Firstly.

In complete contrast to Bravais [72] - Pearson’s “*product - moment coefficient of correlation*” [73, 74] the causal relationship k is defined at every single event, at every

single Bernoulli trial t . Only under conditions where the probability of an event is constant from a Bernoulli trial t to another Bernoulli trial t , it is possible that the causal relationship k passes over into Pearson's phi coefficient [76] but not in general.

Secondly.

Correlation is not causation and vice versa. Causation is not correlation. This is proofed [77] for so many times that it does not make any sense to repeat one self again on this issue.

Thirdly.

Historically, and following Pearson himself it is necessary to consider that "*The fundamental theorems of correlation were for the first time and almost exhaustively discussed by B r a v a i s ('Analyse mathématique sur les probabilités des erreurs de situation d'un point.' Mémoires par divers Savants, T. IX., Paris, 1846, pp. 255-332) nearly half a century ago.*"[74] Furthermore, Karl Pearson (1857-1936) himself "rejected causal thinking"[see 78, p. 39]. Pearson himself has been an advocate of anti-causality in the extreme and much more than that. "Pearson categorically denies the need for an independent concept of causal relation beyond correlation ... he *exterminated* causation from statistics before it had a chance to take root "[see 71, p. 340]. Following Pearson, causation is without any scientific meaning, Pearson demanded unconditionally that "... correlation ... have to replace ... causation "[see 29, p. 157]. In general, "*Pearson's philosophy discouraged him from looking too far behind phenomena.*"[79]

Therefore and completely in contrast to Pearson's demonstrably anti-causal statistical methods[74, 76], the causal relationship k is **defined, derived and valid at every single run of an experiment, at every single Bernoulli trial t .**

5. Conclusion

Formally, experimental and non-experimental data can be analysed for causal relationships without any restriction. However, sample data can be biased and great care is necessary.

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